

Supplementary Material 3

Inter-annual electricity balancing in 100% renewable energy systems assessed through a techno-economic comparison of data series length, e-hydrogen versus e-methane, and multi-objective solutions

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Overview

This document serves as a guide to the comprehensive set of graphical results generated for this research. Due to the extensive nature of the analysis, which produced a large number of individual figures, the complete dataset is hosted in a permanent online repository to ensure full transparency and facilitate further research.

This document provides:

- Direct links to the full dataset.
- A detailed overview of the repository's folder structure.
- An exemplary case study for one region (Finland) to showcase the types of figures available.

The complete, version-controlled dataset is permanently available on Zenodo at the following link:

Full data repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17249273>

Repository structure

The Zenodo repository is organised into two main folders.

Folder 1: 1_Scenarios

This folder contains the complete, detailed graphical outputs for each of the four main simulation runs. Each scenario has dedicated sub-folders:

- **S1 IAS NASA H2R:** NASA data (22 years), e-H₂ for re-electrification. Contains results for 145 regions.
- **S2 IAS NASA CH4R:** NASA data (22 years), e-CH₄ for re-electrification. Contains results for 145 regions.
- **S3 IAS ERA5 H2R:** ERA5 data (85 years), e-H₂ for re-electrification. Contains results for 14 representative regions.
- **S4 IAS ERA5 CH4R:** ERA5 data (85 years), e-CH₄ for re-electrification. Contains results for 14 representative regions.

Within each of these scenario folders (S1 to S4), the results are further organised into seven sub-folders:

- *1_Plots_IAS_OC_Storage_SOC:* Contains three key plots for each individual region:
 1. Storage factor vs. overcapacity Pareto front.
 2. Storage state of charge (SOC) in TWh vs. year.
 3. Storage SOC in percentage vs. year.
- *2_Plots_IAS_Cost_Absolute_tau:* Contains the cost-overcapacity Pareto front for each region, showing absolute costs in b€/a.

- *3 Plots_IAS_Cost Markup_tau*: Contains the cost-overcapacity Pareto front for each region, showing the cost markup in percentage.
- *4 Plots_IAS_worldmaps_MinCost_MinOC*: Contains global map diagrams for the two “corner solutions” (curtailment optimisation and cost optimisation).
- *5 Plots_IAS_worldmaps_tau1*: Contains global map diagrams for the τ_1 solution.
- *6 Plots_IAS_worldmaps_tau2*: Contains global map diagrams for the τ_2 solution.
- *7 Plots_IAS_worldmaps_tau3*: Contains global map diagrams for the τ_3 solution.

Folder 2: 2_Comparative_Analysis

This folder contains figures that directly compare the outcomes of different scenarios, such as the impact of weather data length (NASA vs. ERA5) and the choice of storage technology (e-H₂ vs. e-CH₄).

Exemplary case: Finland (FI)

To illustrate the types of data available, the figures for Finland (FI) from the S4 (ERA5 CH₄R) scenario are presented below as a representative example.

1. Storage factor vs. overcapacity Pareto front

Figure S3.1 shows the trade-off between the required storage factor (SF) and the installed variable renewable energy (VRE) overcapacity for each of the four storage types for Finland (FI).

Figure S3.1. Exemplary storage factor vs. overcapacity Pareto front for Finland (e-CH₄, ERA5 data).

This Figure S3.1 and similar figures for all 14 regions can be found within the downloaded archive in the sub-folders named:

1 Scenarios\S4 IAS ERA5 CH4R\1 Plots_IAS_OC_Storage_SOC

2. Storage state of charge (SOC) vs. year

Figure S3.2 illustrates the year-by-year evolution of the stored energy level over the entire time series, presented in both absolute terms (TWh) and as a percentage of the total storage capacity for Finland (FI).

Figure S3.2. Exemplary storage SOC charts for Finland in TWh (left) and percentage (right) for the e-CH₄ scenario using the 85-year ERA5 dataset.

The similar figures containing storage SOC vs year of 14 selected regions can be found within the downloaded archive at the path:

1 Scenarios\S4 IAS ERA5 CH4R\1 Plots_IAS_OC_Storage_SOC

3. Absolute cost vs. overcapacity Pareto front

Figure S3.3 illustrates the trade-off between the absolute annualised cost of the inter-annual balancing system (in b€/a) and the installed VRE overcapacity for Finland (FI).

Figure S3.3. Exemplary absolute cost vs. overcapacity Pareto front for Finland (e-CH₄, ERA5 data).

The complete set of absolute cost vs. overcapacity Pareto front figures for all 14 regions and scenarios can be accessed within the downloaded archive at:

1 Scenarios\S4 IAS ERA5 CH4R\2 Plots_IAS_Cost_Absolute_tau

4. Cost markup vs. overcapacity Pareto front

Figure S3.4 shows the same trade-off as Figure S3.3, however with the cost presented as a relative markup (%) compared to the baseline 100% renewable energy (RE) system cost of 2050.

Figure S3.4. Exemplary cost markup vs. overcapacity Pareto front for Finland (e-CH₄, ERA5 data).

Similar figures of cost markup vs. overcapacity for all 14 regions can be found within the downloaded archive at the path:

1 Scenarios\S4 IAS ERA5 CH4R\3 Plots_IAS_Cost Markup_tau

5. Comparative map diagrams

The map diagram in Figure S3.5 provide a global overview of the key results and the impact of different methodological choices. The example below shows the relative cost reduction achieved by using e-CH₄ instead of e-H₂.

Figure S3.5. Exemplary map diagram showing the relative cost reduction of the inter-annual storage (IAS) system when using e-CH₄ compared to e-H₂.

Similar comparative global maps and comparative figures can be found from the downloaded archive in the folder named "2 Comparative analysis".